

International Society for Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence (ISVHAAI)

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Abstract: "International Society for Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence (ISVHAAI)". The result of 16 years of my journey in Artificial Intelligence (4 Years at IIT Roorkee. 12 Years after Completing Studies at IIT Roorkee).

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; AI; Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence; VHAAI; International Society for Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence; ISVHAAI

Request for opening a new International Society: With all my efforts I coined (defined) "Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence (VHAAI)".

I request AI Scientists, AI Experts, AI Students and all AI members to open up a new International Society titled - "International Society for Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence (ISVHAAI)". The goal of ISVHAAI is to improve and apply VHAAI for solving various problems.

Initial definition of VHAAI: VHAAI is a new field which is the collection of the following fields:

- 1) Out of the Box Artificial Intelligence (OBAI)
- 2) Artificial Intelligence Plus Plus (AI++)
- 3) Artificial Excellence (AE)
- 4) Artificial God Optimization (AGO)
- 5) Artificial Human Optimization (AHO)
- 6) Artificial Soul Optimization (ASO)
- 7) Twenty Second Century Artificial Intelligence (TSCAI)
- 8) Deep Loving (DL)
- 9) Nature Plus Plus Inspired Computing (N++IC)
- 10) Artificial Satisfaction (AS)
- 11) The Interesting and Complete Artificial Intelligence (ICAI)
- 12) Lord Rama Artificial Intelligence (LRAI)
- 13) Data Science Plus Plus (DS++)
- 14) Stories Inspired Optimization Algorithms (SIOA)

Few Opportunities for Future PhD Titles:

- 1) VHAAI for eradication of Poverty.

- 2) VHAAI for removal of Child Labor.
- 3) VHAAI for changing country from "Developing Country" to "Developed Country".
- 4) VHAAI for decreasing Crimes.
- 5) VHAAI for increasing literacy.
- 6) VHAAI for providing Food, Shelter for all individuals.

Few Opportunities for Future Research Labs:

- 1) IIT VHAAI Research Labs
- 2) IBM VHAAI Research Labs
- 3) Meta VHAAI Research Labs
- 4) Google VHAAI Research Labs

I Repeat this statement - "I request AI Scientists, AI Experts, AI Students and all AI members to open up a new International Society titled - 'International Society for Very Highly Advanced Artificial Intelligence (ISVHAAI)'. The goal of ISVHAAI is to improve and apply VHAAI for solving various problems".

This is just the beginning of VHAAI.

#ai #artificialintelligence #VeryHighlyAdvancedArtificialIntelligence #VHAAI #iit #iitroorkee
#InternationalSocietyForVHAAI #ISVHAAI #request #TheBeginning